

1.5-15.5 GHz cryogenic low noise balanced amplifier report

**Units: Y214G1014-15+YH903023-21 and
Y214G1016-18+YH903024-22**

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Change Record

Revision	Date	Affected Paragraphs(s)	Reason/Initiation/Remarks
A	2019-06-07	All	First Issue
B	2019-07-15	Section 3, par. 1	Corrected mistake in type of cold attenuator used: changed GaAs for quartz.
C	2020-06-18	Cover	Removed confidential warning

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1.5-15.5 GHz BALANCED AMPLIFIER REPORT

1. Introduction

This report presents 1.5-15.5 GHz low noise cryogenic balanced amplifiers, designed and built at the *Observatorio de Yebes* for the development of a receiver for the European VLBI network in the framework of the BRAND Joint Research Activity.

The balanced amplifier configuration has the advantage of attaining good return losses with little noise penalty as compared to a single ended amplifier or an isolator plus amplifier combination. This approach to the front-end amplifier of BRAND was selected after a comparative study reported in [1]. A 1.5-15.5 GHz balanced amplifier unit comprises two 3 dB 90° hybrid couplers YH90 (Fig. 1), two LNAs Y214G (Fig. 2) and a couple of matched loads assembled according to Fig. 3.

Low noise cryogenic amplifiers Y214G are ultra-wide-band amplifiers designed for the VGOS next generation geodetic VLBI band, with an average noise temperature in the 1.5-15.5 GHz band of 6.5 K.

YH90214 are 5 stages 3 dB 90° hybrid couplers originally designed for the 2-14 GHz band and modified for best performance in the 1.5-15.5 GHz band. They yield an amplitude unbalance lower than ± 0.7 dB in 95% of the band and, insertion losses lower than 0.4 dB and return losses below 17 dB.

This document includes a description of the amplifier and how to operate it, details about the tests performed, the measurements techniques utilized and datasheets and plots with the relevant data collected.

The unit should be biased by a **servo controlled power supply**, which sets the gate voltage for any selected drain current. A power supply could be provided with the LNA or, alternatively, details about a NRAO style power supply produced for TTI¹ for our HEMT amplifiers are available upon request.

¹ TTI Norte, Santander (Spain) www.ttinorte.es

Figure 1: External view of a YH90 hybrid coupler. Dimensions excluding connectors are 49.7×14×14 mm (X×Y×Z in the picture)

Figure 2: External view of a Y214G LNA. Dimensions excluding connectors are 20×22×9 mm (X×Y×Z in the picture)

Figure 3: Assembled balanced amplifier picture (without the matched loads).and schematic. Length of the assembly excluding connectors is 82 mm. The orientation of the LNAs can be changed by rotating them a maximum of approx. 140° around the connectors. Input is on the left and output on the right. Matched loads can be placed both on ports 1 or both on ports 4 of the hybrids in the picture, leaving the other couple of ports for input and output.

2. Description and operating procedures of the amplifier

2.1 Dimensions and mechanical interfaces

The balanced amplifier is shipped disassembled. The LNAs and hybrids should be connected upon arrival following the placement indications of a picture included in the measurement report of each unit.

Figures 4 and 5 show an outside view of an amplifier with the external dimensions and mechanical interfaces in two possible orientations of the LNAs relative to the hybrids. Drawings of the hybrid and the amplifier with more detailed dimensions are shown in figures 6 and 7.

The amplifier and the hybrid chassis are made of aluminum. The LNAs are plated with soft gold.

Several M2 threaded holes, which can be seen on the bottom side of the LNA and hybrid chassis in figures 6 and 7, can be used for thermal anchoring. The noise performance of the unit is very sensitive to the input hybrid temperature. Special care should be taken to ensure the best possible cooling of this component. Dedicated thermal straps for the LNAs (and, if possible, the output hybrid) are also recommended.

Figure 4: External dimensions of the balanced amplifier with the LNAs in position 90° (minimal width)

Figure 5: External dimensions of the balanced amplifier with the LNAs in position 20° (minimal height)

2.2 Electrical interfaces

Input and output ports are female field replaceable SMA coaxial connectors.

The **DC bias connector** of each individual LNA is a 9 pin microminiature D-type ITT-Cannon. The pin out is provided in figure 7. The bias settings are given in the “Measurement report” section.

Figure 6: 3 dB 90° hybrid coupler YH90214 external dimensions, mechanical and electrical interfaces

Figure 7: Low noise amplifier Y214G1 mechanical and electrical interfaces, external dimensions and DC pinout.

2.3 Bias and ESD

Each amplifier unit has three active stages, two of which include very **ESD** sensitive of InP HEMT transistors; caution must be taken during the manipulation and operation of the unit. Each gate bias circuit built in the amplifier include two GaAs Schottky diodes in antiparallel ($V_F \approx 0.8 \text{ V @ } 15 \text{ K}$) which limit the gate voltages to prevent damage to the transistors. A 1 nF capacitor acts as a charge divider reducing the ESD impact. Information on ESD prevention

procedures and safe unit handling and storage is provided in the “ESD and power supply leakage protection of InP HEMT cryogenic amplifiers” section of the report.

The nominal **bias** condition selected for the amplifiers optimizes the device for noise, gain, ripple, reflection and gain compression.

Never exceed a drain voltage/current of 1.5 V / 10 mA for InP/InAs transistors. Note that the first stage has two transistors in parallel and therefore admits roughly twice this current. A schematic of the bias circuits is shown in figure 8. There is a significant voltage drop in the drain lines due to the 120-170 Ω total series resistance – which is taken into account in the given bias settings. Note also that the 1.5 V limit is set in the transistor drain, after the voltage drop in the bias resistors.

Figure 8: Bias circuit (inside each amplifier)

3. Measurements

Noise temperature (and gain) was measured with a system based on a computer controlled Agilent N8975A Noise Figure Meter described in detail in [2], [3]. Room temperature data were obtained with an Agilent N4000A noise diode. The DUT is cooled in a Dewar with a CTI 1020 refrigerator. Cryogenic measurements were taken with the “cold attenuator” method, using an Agilent N4002A noise diode (at room temperature) plus a special 15 dB attenuator in a quartz substrate cooled at cryogenic temperature. The attenuator temperature is carefully monitored by a Lake Shore sensor diode. An absolute accuracy (@ 2σ) of 14 K at $T_{amb}=297$ K and 1.7 K at $T_{amb}=14$ K can be estimated with methods presented in [4]. Repeatability is better than these values by an order of magnitude.

S parameters were measured in the same Dewar with an Agilent E8364B Vector Network Analyzer from 0.1 to 20.1 GHz. A detailed description of the measurement procedure used at cryogenic temperature can be found in [2], [3]. The amplifier output is connected to one of the stainless steel Dewar transitions and its input to another through a semi-flexible Cu cable. A full two port calibration is done at room temperature with a Agilent N4693-60001 electronic calibration kit in place of the amplifier inside the Dewar, with the same cable. The stainless steel lines are supposed to be invariant with temperature. The semi-flexible Cu cable is measured at cryogenic temperature independently and its loss variation is taken into account to correct S11 and S21. Time domain gating is used to correct for the residual reflection changes in the lines.

1 dB compression at the input is measured with the same VNA in power sweep mode and a HP 8487A Power Sensor together with a HP 437B Power Meter are used for absolute power calibration and cable losses measurement. Linearity was checked at 3, 6 and 12 GHz. Data is presented only for 3 GHz, frequency for which the worst values were obtained.

Additional measurements to ensure the absence of oscillations of the amplifiers were performed at room and cryogenic temperatures.

The amplifier report which follows this page contains:

- 1) Data-sheet:
Amplifier identification, nominal bias and a summary of the measurements performed at room and cryogenic temperature.
- 2) Noise and gain plots: Noise temperature and available gain at room and cryogenic temperature. Gain curves are taken with the Vector Network Analyzer and with the Noise Figure Meter during noise measurements.
- 3) Return loss plots: $|S_{11}|$ and $|S_{22}|$ at room and cryogenic temperature
- 4) 1 dB compression plot: Output power and gain curves at cryogenic temperature for 3 GHz.
- 5) Assembly arrangement: Photograph of the balanced LNA showing the disposition of the LNAs and hybrids during the measurements.

References

- [1] J. D. Gallego, I. López-Fernández, I. Malo, A. García, C. Diez, R. I. Amils; “*Ultra-wide Band LNAs for BRAND Front-ends: Single-ended and Balanced Approaches*”, Technical Report BRAND/Yeb TR 2018-001; 12/02/2018
- [2] J. D. Gallego, I. López-Fernández, C. Diez, “*A Measurement Test Set for ALMA Band 9 Amplifiers*”, 1st Radionet Engineering Forum Workshop, 23-24/06/2009, Gothenburg (available at http://www.radionet-eu.org/fp7wiki/lib/exe/fetch.php?media=na:engineering:ew:lopez-fernandez_final.pdf)
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- [4] J. D. Gallego, J. L. Cano, “*Estimation of Uncertainty in Noise Measurements Using Monte Carlo Analysis*”, 1st Radionet Engineering Forum Workshop, 23-24/06/2009, Gothenburg (available at http://www.radionet-eu.org/fp7wiki/lib/exe/fetch.php?media=na:engineering:ew:gallego_final.pdf)

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CRYO BALANCED LNA DATA SHEET

DATE: 27/12/18

BAND: 1.5- 15.5 GHz S/N: Y214G1016/18+YH903024/22

TRTs (BOTH LNAs): ST1: 2xT-328 ST2: T-78 ST3: T-57

ROOM TEMPERATURE DATA T = 296

NOMINAL BIAS (EQUAL FOR BOTH LNAs)	$V_{d1} = 4.0$	$I_{d1} = 20.0$	$V_{g1} \approx 0.00$	
	$V_{d2} = 2.0$	$I_{d2} = 10.0$	$V_{g2} \approx -0.21$	
	$V_{d3} = 3.0$	$I_{d3} = 15.0$	$V_{g3} \approx -0.17$	
	FREQUENCY BAND:	2-14	4.6-13.8	1.5-15.5
MEASUREMENTS	AVERAGE NOISE TEMP:	101.6	109.9	109.5
	AVERAGE GAIN:	29.3	29.0	29.4
	MIN. INPUT RETURN LOSS:	-16.4	-18.6	-13.5
	MIN. OUTPUT RETURN LOSS:	-18.9	-18.9	-18.9

CRYOGENIC TEMPERATURE DATA T = 16.2

NOMINAL BIAS (EQUAL FOR BOTH LNAs) ($P_{diss} = 84.60$ mW)	$V_{d1} = 2.80$	$I_{d1} = 12.0$	$V_{g1} \approx 0.04$	
	$V_{d2} = 1.20$	$I_{d2} = 5.0$	$V_{g2} \approx -0.11$	
	$V_{d3} = 3.00$	$I_{d3} = 15.0$	$V_{g3} \approx -0.11$	
	FREQUENCY BAND:	2-14	4.6-13.8	1.5-15.5
MEASUREMENTS	AVERAGE NOISE TEMP:	7.8	8.2	8.2
	MIN. - MAX. NOISE TEMP:	5.1-11.3	6.5-11.3	5.1-14.5
	AVERAGE GAIN:	33.8	33.5	33.7
	GAIN SPAN FULL BAND / 2 GHz	3.3 / 1.2	1.8 / 0.8	3.3 / 1.2
	MIN. INPUT RETURN LOSS:	-17.5	-19.2	-12.8
	MIN. OUTPUT RETURN LOSS:	-20.5	-20.5	-19.8
	MIN. INPUT 1dB COMPRESSION:	-30.1		

REMARKS: Gain data from VNA measurements
 Coaxial noise measurements according to cold att. method
 Other bias settings are available to:
 Reduce power dissipation at the expense of either noise or 1 dB compression
 Improve 1 dB compression increasing the power dissipation

V_d in Volts, I_d in mA, Noise temperature in K, Gain and Return loss in dB, Frequency band in GHz

Y214G1016/18+YH903024/22

$V_{D(1,2,3)} = (4,2,3)$

$I_{D(1,2,3)} = (20,10,15)$

T=296

Y214G1016/18+YH903024/22

$V_{D(1,2,3)} = (2.8,1.2,3)$

$I_{D(1,2,3)} = (12,5,15)$

T=16.2

1016/18+3024/22

VD(4,2,3)

ID(20,10,15)

T=300

1016/18+3024/22

VD=(2.8,1.2,3)

ID=(12,5,15)

T=16

Assembly arrangement of Y214G1016/18+YH903024/22 for this measurement report

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CRYO BALANCED LNA DATA SHEET

DATE: 27/12/18

BAND: 1.5- 15.5 GHz S/N: Y214G1014/15+YH903023/21

TRTs (BOTH LNAs): ST1: 2xT-328 ST2: T-78 ST3: T-57

ROOM TEMPERATURE DATA T = 296

NOMINAL BIAS (EQUAL FOR BOTH LNAs)	$V_{d1} = 4.0$	$I_{d1} = 20.0$	$V_{g1} \approx 0.02$	
	$V_{d2} = 2.0$	$I_{d2} = 10.0$	$V_{g2} \approx -0.22$	
	$V_{d3} = 3.0$	$I_{d3} = 15.0$	$V_{g3} \approx -0.17$	
	FREQUENCY BAND:	2-14	4.6-13.8	1.5-15.5
MEASUREMENTS	AVERAGE NOISE TEMP:	102.0	110.8	111.0
	AVERAGE GAIN:	29.3	29.0	29.3
	MIN. INPUT RETURN LOSS:	-15.9	-17.3	-12.3
	MIN. OUTPUT RETURN LOSS:	-18.1	-18.1	-17.6

CRYOGENIC TEMPERATURE DATA T = 17.1

NOMINAL BIAS (EQUAL FOR BOTH LNAs) ($P_{diss} = 85.10$ mW)	$V_{d1} = 2.80$	$I_{d1} = 12.0$	$V_{g1} \approx 0.04$	
	$V_{d2} = 1.30$	$I_{d2} = 5.0$	$V_{g2} \approx -0.16$	
	$V_{d3} = 3.00$	$I_{d3} = 15.0$	$V_{g3} \approx -0.11$	
	FREQUENCY BAND:	2-14	4.6-13.8	1.5-15.5
MEASUREMENTS	AVERAGE NOISE TEMP:	7.6	8.2	8.1
	MIN. - MAX. NOISE TEMP:	4.8-11.9	6.2-11.9	4.8-15.2
	AVERAGE GAIN:	34.1	33.8	34.1
	GAIN SPAN FULL BAND / 2 GHz:	4.1 / 1.5	2.2 / 0.9	4.1 / 1.5
	MIN. INPUT RETURN LOSS:	-16.6	-17.6	-10.7
	MIN. OUTPUT RETURN LOSS:	-18.9	-18.9	-17.7
	MIN. INPUT 1dB COMPRESSION:	-29.8		

REMARKS: Gain data from VNA measurements
 Coaxial noise measurements according to cold att. method
 Other bias settings are available to:
 Reduce power dissipation at the expense of either noise or 1 dB compression
 Improve 1 dB compression increasing the power dissipation

V_d in Volts, I_d in mA, Noise temperature in K, Gain and Return loss in dB, Frequency band in GHz

Y214G1014/15+YH903023/21

 $V_{D(1,2,3)} = (4,2,3)$ $I_{D(1,2,3)} = (20,10,15)$

T=296

Y214G1014/15+YH903023/21

 $V_{D(1,2,3)} = (2.8,1.3,3)$ $I_{D(1,2,3)} = (12,5,15)$

T=17.1

1014/15+3023/21

VD(4,2,3)

ID(20,10,15)

T=300

1014/15+3023/21

VD=(2.8,1.2,3)

ID=(12,5,15)

T=16

Assembly arrangement of Y214G1014/15+YH903023/21 for this measurement report

ESD AND POWER SUPPLY LEAKAGE PROTECTION OF CRYOGENIC HEMT AMPLIFIERS

Introduction

Cryogenic amplifiers made with InP, InAs and metamorphic GaAs HEMTs have been found to be very sensitive to ESD (electrostatic discharges) and leakage from the power supplies. The handling of these devices requires especial precautions beyond the normal care taken with cryogenic amplifiers made with commercial GaAs HEMTs. Especial procedures should be followed during assembly of the amplifiers as well as during tests and operation to avoid permanent damage to the devices. The most common mode of failure is the total or partial destruction of the gate of the transistors. Partially damaged devices may lose one or more gate fingers and show poor or no pinch off, even if the gate junction still show diode characteristics. Totally damaged devices may appear as a short circuit (or low resistance) from drain to source. Sometimes, but not often, the device may appear as an open circuit.

ESD is not the only problem. Leakage of soldering irons, bonding machines and even power supplies of the amplifiers has produced many failures. All the equipment used in the assembly test and operation of the amplifiers should be checked for leakage. Most of the field problems detected have been caused by 50 Hz current leakage of input transformers of floating DC power supplies. This leakage is due to the capacitive coupling between primary and secondary of the transformers and it is always present unless there is a grounded faraday shield between the two windings or other especial precautions are taken

Procedure for assembly of the amplifiers (manufacturer only)

1. Technicians manipulating amplifiers should wear grounded wrist straps.
2. The bench for the assembly of the amplifiers should have a dissipative mat connected to ground.
3. A short circuit should be put in the power connector of the amplifier at all times during assembly (the short circuit should short all pins together to the case). The short circuit will only be removed for testing the amplifier or when connected for operation.
4. Coaxial SMA short circuits should be connected to input and output RF connectors at all times during assembly. The short circuits will only be removed for testing the amplifier or when connected for operation.
5. The soldering irons used for assembly should be adequately grounded. It should be checked that no voltage respect to ground is measured on the tip with the soldering iron on and off. The maximum voltage allowed will be 0.020 Vrms respect to ground measured with a high input impedance ($> 10 \text{ M}\Omega$) voltmeter in AC mode.
6. The tip of the bonding and welding machines used for assembly of the amplifier should be adequately grounded. It should be checked that no voltage respect to ground is measured with machines on or off. The maximum voltage allowed will be 0.020 Vrms respect to ground measured with a high input impedance ($> 10 \text{ M}\Omega$) voltmeter in AC mode.

7. Be very careful with any measurement instrument used during assembly. If ohmmeters are used for verification of internal cabling, battery operated units are preferred. Make all necessary verifications before the assembly of the transistors when possible. The assembly of the transistors should be the last operation to avoid unnecessary risks.

Procedure for test and operation of the amplifiers

1. The amplifier should be kept with a short circuit in the power connector when not in use. The short circuit should short all pins together and to the case. The short circuit should only be removed if adequate ESD and leakage protection precautions have been taken.
2. Most failures in cryogenic amplifiers are produced when connecting or disconnecting the amplifier to/from the power supply. **A very careful procedure should be followed.**
3. Make sure that the power supply is **off** before connecting or disconnecting the power supply cable to/from the amplifier.
4. Make sure that the power supply and the amplifier are connected to the same protective ground before connecting or disconnecting the power supply cable to/from the amplifier.
5. Very especial care should be taken in case of a DC power supply floating respect to the protective ground. This produces most failures. It is safer to connect the **return** terminal at the output of the DC power supply to the protective **ground** permanently on the power supply side. If this is not possible (for example to avoid ground loops with long cables), a provisional connection from the return of the power supply to the amplifier case should be **made prior to any connection or disconnection** of the power supply cable. Always make sure that there is no voltage between the return of the power supply and the protective ground (case of the amplifier) before connecting the power supply cable. The maximum allowed voltage will be 0.020 Vrms measured with a high input impedance ($> 10 \text{ M}\Omega$) voltmeter in AC mode.
6. The power supply should have adequate built in protection to avoid excessive voltage and currents in the transistors in case of power supply failure and during the transients produced when the power supply is switched on or off. Adequate Zenner diodes can be used in parallel with the outputs, and adequate series resistors in series. If the protections are designed adequately, the amplifier will survive even in case of errors in the connections of the cables.

Storage of the amplifiers

1. The amplifiers should be stored in a clean dry anti-static environment.
2. The amplifier should be stored with short circuits in the power and RF connectors.
3. For permanent storage desiccators with less than 20% relative humidity should be used. The preferred method of storage is in dry nitrogen containers.
4. For transportation, and for short-term storage, anti-static plastic bags with silica gel bags to keep low relative humidity should be used.